

Comparative evaluation of anticorrosion properties of HENNA leaves powder on Tin in acidic and alkaline media

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ABSTRACT

The corrosion inhibition behavior of Tin in 1.0 M HCl and 1.0 M NaOH solutions using weight loss technique was investigated at temperature ranges, 25-50 °C. The inhibition efficiency of tin in each media by using the leaves of *Lawsonia inermis*, *L* powder was found to be 93.10% at 50 °C and 95.45% at 30 °C and at optimum inhibitor concentration (0.5%) in which the overall results obtained showed that the extract have good performance and could be used to prevent the corrosion of the metal in the tested media. The leaves extract of *Lawsonia inermis* is the most effective in alkaline solution. At lower concentration of 0.1%, the inhibition efficiency was found to be 31.03% at 50 °C and 50% at 30 °C. This revealed that the inhibition efficiency decreased with increased in temperature but increased with increasing inhibitor concentrations. The research also include determination of activation energy, Gibbs free energy whose values are 28.131, 29.589 kJmol⁻¹; -3.280, -3.245 kJmol⁻¹ in acidic and alkaline media respectively, in addition to calculation of the degree of surface coverage whose data was used in the investigation or approximation of the inhibitor adsorption characteristics and its relation with the different adsorption isotherms. The adsorption was found to obey Freundlich isotherm with linear coefficient (R^2) and equilibrium parameter (K_{ads}) to be 0.972, 0.957; 0.06, 0.05 for both systems in acidic and alkaline media respectively. Physical adsorption mechanism is proposed from the trend of ΔG_{ads} . The negative values of ΔG_{ads} show the spontaneity of the inhibition process. The increase in the activation energy of the inhibition processes with values less than the threshold value of 80kJ/mol support the mechanism of physical adsorption process.

Keywords Corrosion, Tin, Henna leaves powder, HCl, NaOH

1. Introduction

Corrosion had influenced in the food industries, causing enormous wastage of food substances due to metallic contamination, as a result it lead to huge economic losses to canning industries. As contribution to the current interest on environmentally friendly, green corrosion inhibitors, therefore, the present study investigates the possibility of using Henna leaves powder for the inhibition of the corrosion of tin in HCl and NaOH solutions using the mass loss method in the acidic and alkaline solutions. An aqueous extract of plant material *Lawsonia Inermis L* powder had been used as a corrosion inhibitor in controlling corrosion of carbon steel immersed in an aqueous solution containing 60 ppm of Cl^- , by the mass loss method in the absence and presence of Zn^{2+} . The main constituent of this plant extract is Lawsone. It has excellent inhibition efficiency (IE) and shows excellent IE at pH 6, 8 and 12. In the presence of Zn^{2+} there exists a synergistic effect. The protective film has been analyzed using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy [1]. The corrosion inhibition of carbon steel in the presence of different concentrations of aqueous extract from henna leaves in 1 M HCl solution was using the weight loss methods. *Lawsonia inermis L*, commonly known as “Henna”. It is also called *Lalle* in Hausa language, is a well branched shrub frequently cultivated in many tropical and warm temperature regions of Nigeria. The dyeing properties and corrosion inhibition were attributed to the presence of Lawsone, 2-hydroxy-1, 4-naphthaquinone having color index number 75486 [2]. The structure of the active compound is as shown in scheme 1 and 2 under the discussion of the inhibition mechanism of the reaction mixture.

2. Materials and Methods

All the reagents used in this research were of analytical grade and deionized water was used for their preparation. The Tin sheet used for the study is obtained from metal focus fabrication technology incubation center complex, farm center Kano State, Nigeria. The sheet was mechanically pressed-cut into coupons, each of dimensions 2.0 cm × 2.0 cm × 0.001 cm containing a small hole drilled near the upper edge. Each coupon was degreased by washing with ethanol, dipped in acetone and allowed to dry in air before they were preserved in a desiccator [3]. The volume of the Tin sheet sample was measured by the method of displacement of water by the metal [4]. Hence, the density g/cm^3 of the metal was determined by dividing its mass by the obtained volume. Fresh leaves of the Henna plant were obtained from a garden and identified at the Plant Science Department of Bayero University, Kano with Herbarium Accession Number BUKHAN 0379. The leaves were then washed with deionized water after collection and air dried. The leaves were ground into fine powder form and were sieved to pass through a 250 nm meshed sieve. The solution was prepared by weighing 1.0 g of the Henna powder in to 1000ml volumetric flask containing 1.0 M HCl solution, made up to the mark with test solution, shake to dissolved and left to stand for 24 hours. This represent the stock solution of the inhibitor (1000 mg/L) from which various concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 mg/L were prepared by serial dilution. Similar procedure was repeated with 1M sodium hydroxide solution [5]. A previously treated and weighed coupon was separately and completely immersed in a 100 ml beaker containing the test solution at a specified concentration with and without the inhibitor. The beaker was inserted into a thermo stated Gallenhamb Water bath: made in England manufactured by Medical instrument MFG. CO. 400013 maintained at a specified temperature. The coupon was withdrawn from the test solution at intervals of time, it was then washed with deionized water and light brush, dried in acetone and reweighed. The difference in weight was taken as the weight loss due to corrosion to test the effect of temperature and inhibitor concentration [3]. FTIR analysis (Cary 630 FTIR Spectrometer Agilent Technologies) using Attenuated total reflection technique was used to identify the major functional groups and bond present.

The degree of surface coverage (θ), inhibition efficiency (% I.E) of the inhibitor and corrosion rates (CR in mm/y) were calculated from the average weight loss using the following Equations 1, 2 and 3 [6].

$$\theta = \frac{\Delta w_1 - \Delta w_2}{\Delta w_1} \quad (1)$$

$$\% \text{I.E} = \frac{\Delta w_1 - \Delta w_2}{\Delta w_1} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where ΔW_1 and ΔW_2 are the weight loss of the metal in uninhibited and inhibited solution, respectively.

$$\text{Corrosion rate (mm/y)} = \frac{\Delta w \times 87.6}{A \times t \times d} \quad (3)$$

Where, ΔW is weight loss in mg, A is area of specimen in cm^2 , t is time of exposure in hours, d is the density of metal in g/cm^3 and 87.6 is a constant number known as reactivity constant of Tin.

The basic process of metallic corrosion in aqueous solution consists of the anodic dissolution of metal and the cathodic reduction of oxidants present in the solution. A typical example of this is when tin is placed in hydrochloric acid it dissolves forming Tin chloride with the release of hydrogen gas. Similarly, NaOH solution attack Tin which dissolves

forming sodium stannate (a colorless complex salt and octahedral in shape) with the release of hydrogen gas. During metallic corrosion, the rate of oxidation equals to the rate of reduction in terms of electron production and consumption [7].

Acidic Media

Basic Media

This involve two step mechanisms

First step half-cell mechanism:

Second step half-cell mechanism:

Overall reaction:

3. Results

Table 1 Weight loss values and corrosion rate for varied temperature in 1.0M acid and alkaline solution without inhibitor.

S/N	Temperature (K)	Average weight loss in Acid (g)	Average weight loss in Alkaline (g)	Acid C.R (mm/y)	Alkaline C.R (mm/y)
1	298	0.0026	0.0021	37960	22995
2	303	0.0027	0.0022	39420	24090
3	308	0.0028	0.0024	40880	26280
4	313	0.0030	0.0026	43800	28470
5	318	0.0032	0.0027	46720	29565
6	323	0.0035	0.0029	51100	31755

Table 2 Weight loss, degree of surface coverage (DSC), inhibition efficiency (IE) and corrosion rate (CR) for varied concentration of Henna extract in 1.0 M HCl and 1.0 M NaOH solutions for 3hrs and 4hrs respectively at 323K.

INH. Conc. (mg/L)	ACIDIC MEDIUM				BASIC MEDIUM			
	Wt. loss (g)	DSC (θ)	IE (%IE)	CR (mm/y)	Wt. loss (g)	DSC (θ)	IE (%IE)	CR (mm/y)
10	0.0026	0.2571	25.71	37960	0.0020	0.3103	31.03	21900
20	0.0018	0.4857	48.57	26280	0.0017	0.4138	41.38	18615
30	0.0015	0.5714	57.14	21900	0.0013	0.5517	55.17	14235
40	0.0012	0.6571	65.71	17520	0.0008	0.7241	72.41	8760
50	0.0008	0.7714	77.14	11680	0.0002	0.9310	93.10	2190

4. Discussion

4.1. Effect of temperature on weight loss, corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency

There is a slightly increase in weight loss as the temperature is increased from 298–323 K (Table 1). This observation implies that temperature favours the reactivity of the active constituents of the corrosion media. A rise in the temperature usually increases the rate of hydrogen evolution reaction on the cathode, which results in a higher metal corrosion rate. This shows that the dissolution of the metal coupons increased at higher temperatures. It is also evident that a combination of higher temperatures produced higher weight loss with time, thus higher rate of reaction. This observation

Table 3 Weight loss, degree of surface coverage (DSC), inhibition efficiency (IE) and corrosion rate (CR) for varied concentration of Henna extract in 1.0 M HCl and 1.0 M NaOH Solutions for 3hrs and 4hrs respectively at 303K.

INH. Conc. (mg/L)	ACIDIC MEDIUM				BASIC MEDIUM			
	Wt. loss (g)	DSC (θ)	IE (%IE)	CR (mm/y)	Wt. loss (g)	DSC (θ)	IE (%IE)	CR (mm/y)
10	0.0013	0.5185	51.90	18980	0.0011	0.5000	50.00	12045
20	0.0011	0.5926	59.26	16060	0.0009	0.5909	59.09	9855
30	0.0009	0.6667	66.67	13140	0.0005	0.7727	77.27	5475
40	0.007	0.7407	74.07	10220	0.0003	0.8640	86.40	329
50	0.0004	0.8519	85.19	5840	0.0001	0.9545	95.45	110

is attributed to the general rule guiding the rate of chemical reaction, which says that chemical reaction increases with increasing temperatures [8]. However, inhibition decreases with increase in temperature. From Table 1, 2 and 3, it can be observed also that as temperature change from 323 to 303 in the presence of an inhibitor at optimum concentration, there is a corresponding decrease in the weight loss and decrease in the corrosion rate in the range 17520-110 mm/y resulted in the higher inhibition efficiency 93.1 and 95.45%. The maximum inhibition efficiency is lower at 323 K than at 303 K. This is in agreement with what is known about the dependence of adsorption on temperature, that as temperature rises, the quantity adsorbed decreases and as a result of this, the isotherm of higher temperatures are lower than that of lower temperatures [9].

4.2. Effect of inhibitor on the corrosion rate of Tin metal

There was a general reduction in the weight loss of tin sheet in the solutions containing *Lawsonia inermis* compared to the uninhibited solutions. Table 1 shows the variation of corrosion rate in the absence of the inhibitor at temperature range 298-323 K while the Tables' 2 and 3 in the presence of inhibitor with varying concentration of inhibitors at 323 K and 303 K, it also shows the values of inhibition efficiencies and degree of surface coverage obtained from weight loss measurement of different concentrations of Henna extract as compared to the weight loss and corrosion rates of tin in free acid and alkaline solutions at 303 and 323 K in a thermostatic water bath. From the data it was observed that corrosion rate was significantly lowered down in presence of the inhibitors than in their absent and also it is clear that the surface coverage (θ) increases with increasing concentration of inhibitor but decreases with increase in temperature. This effect is hugely marked at optimum concentration (0.5%) of the inhibitors. The corrosion rate was found dependent on the concentration of inhibitors and temperature. The decreasing corrosion rate and increasing inhibition efficiency was attributed to the fact that the adsorption of inhibitor on the metal surface blocked the corrosion sites of metal surface [3]. This implies that the Henna extract bonded and adheres on the surface of corroding environment and produced a protective film on the metal. The adsorbed films of the inhibitors act as physical barrier between metal surface and corrosion media [10]. The mechanisms of the reactions are proposed below.

Scheme 2 Henna in basic medium forms of lawsone.

In the acidic solution of Henna (Scheme 1), the oxygen atom of the lawsone of the inhibitor can be protonated easily, because there is high electron density on it leading to positively charged inhibitor species while in the basic solution (Scheme 2), the hydrogen atom of the phenolic group in lawsone can be deprotonated by the high electron density of hydroxides ions from the base leading to negatively charged inhibitor species. The adsorption can occur via electrostatic interaction between the charged molecules and the charged on the metal surface leading to physisorption of the inhibitor molecules. Further co-ordinate bond may occur between unshared e^- pairs of unprotonated oxygen atom of the inhibitor and vacant d-orbital of metal surface atoms [11].

4.3. Adsorption and thermodynamic study

Equation 12, is Freundlich isotherm equations and its dimensionless equilibrium parameters Where, K_{ads} is the adsorption equilibrium constant, 55.5 is the water concentration, C is the inhibitor concentration and a is the adsorbate interaction parameter, equation 13 is a thermodynamics equations for activation energy of corrosion process where, A is Arrhenius pre-exponential frequency factor, T is the absolute temperature, R is the universal gas constant, E_a is a quantity characteristic of the adsorption known as activation energy. Equation 14 is a Gibb's free energy of adsorptions, equation 15 and 16 were used to find the enthalpy, entropy and free energy of uninhibited corrosion processes [12].

$$\log \theta = \log K + n \log C \quad (12)$$

$$\log (CR) = \log A - E_a / (2.303RT) \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta G_{ads} = -2.303RT \log [55.5 K_{ads}] \quad (14)$$

$$\log \left(\frac{CR}{T} \right) = \log \left(\frac{R}{Nh} \right) + \frac{\Delta S_{corr}}{2.303R} - \frac{\Delta H_{corr}}{2.303RT} \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta G_{corr} = \Delta H_{corr} - T\Delta S_{corr} \quad (16)$$

Figure 1 Freundlich isotherms for Henna in the acidic and alkal media.

The plot of $\log\theta$ against inhibitor concentration (mg/L) displays a straight line for the tested inhibitor in the acidic and alkaline media using equation 12. The linear plots, with high correlation coefficient (R^2) as presented in Figure 1 with slope of about unity in both media, clearly reveal that the surface adsorption process of the inhibitor molecules on the tin surface followed the Freundlich adsorption isotherm which gives relative higher values of $K_{ads} = 0.06$ and 0.05 for both system in acidic and alkaline media respectively. This indicates that the adsorbing species occupies typical adsorption site at the metal/solution interface as can be seen by the good fit inhibitors. Generally larger K values imply more efficient adsorption, hence a better inhibitive performance [5, 9]. The adsorption of the inhibitor on to the surface of Tin is retarded by increase in temperature supporting the mechanism of physical adsorption. A negative surface charge will favour the adsorption of cations whereas anion adsorption is favoured by a positive surface charge [13]. The ability of Cl^- and OH^- ions in hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide to be strongly adsorbed on the metal surface and hence facilitate physical adsorption of inhibitor is an important consideration. Arrhenius equation was used to study the effect of temperature [3]. The calculated values for the activation energy, the free energy of both uninhibited and inhibited process of the system can be observed in Table 4.

Table 4 Calculated values for activation energy, free energy and equilibrium constant of adsorbed inhibitor system as well as enthalpy and entropy of the corrosion process.

	Acid				Alkaline			
With inhibitor	E_a	ΔG_{ads}	K_{ads}		E_a	ΔG_{ads}	K_{ads}	
	(KJ/mol)	(KJ/mol)			(KJ/mol)	(KJ/mol)		
	28.131	-3.245	0.0603		29.589	-3.280	0.0611	
Without inhibitor	E_a	$\Delta G_{corr.}$	ΔH	ΔS	E_a	$\Delta G_{corr.}$	ΔH	ΔS
	(KJ/mol)	(KJ/mol)	(KJmol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(KJ/mol)	(KJ/mol)	(KJ/mol)	(KJmol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(KJ/mol)
	9.405	-75.539	6.826	0.255	10.562	-74.382	7.983	0.255

From the result obtained the activation energy of basic medium was found to be higher than acidic medium which indicates reaction in basic solution require the higher energy as such take a longer time for the corrosion process. The central idea here is that for the 1.0 M solution of the acid and base to attack the tin, its molecules must then be activated over an energy barrier equal to the E_a of the HCl and NaOH solutions and its temperature dependent. Cruz *et al*, (2004) reported that when the values of $E_a > 80$ kJ/mol, it indicates chemical adsorption and when $E_a < 80$ kJ/mol means physical adsorption. All the estimated values of the activated energy in this work were found to be less than 80 kJ/mol which implies physical adsorption [14]. The negative values of ΔG_{ads}^0 ensure the spontaneity of adsorption process as well as stability of the adsorbed layer on the tin surface. Generally, the values of ΔG_{ads}^0 around -20kJ/mol or lower are consistent with physical adsorption [9].

4.4. FTIR analysis

Figure 2 FTIR absorbance spectra of pure Tin sheet before corroding.

Figure 3 FTIR absorbance spectrum of *Lawsonia inermis* leaves powder.

Figure 4 FTIR absorbance spectra of tin metal in 1.0M HCl with *Lawsonia inermis*.

Figure 5 FTIR absorbance spectra of tin metal in 1.0M NaOH with *Lawsonia inermis*.

The Tin interaction with Henna is due to the presence of free oxygen located at position 2 and 6 and likely the presence of π -electrons as presented in the scheme 1 and 2. The C=O bond ranges from 1630 to 1820 cm^{-1} . The results were confirmed by FTIR spectra of Plant extract and Sn-sheet surface immersed in 1 M HCl and 1 M NaOH with 50 mg/L of Henna extract (Figure 2 to 5). The main constituent of Henna extract is lawsone. It contains benzene unit, p-benzoquinone unit and phenolic group. The-OH bond ranges from 3200-3650 cm^{-1} [15]. The phenolic -OH stretching appears at 3272 cm^{-1} . The peaks at 2920 and 2106 cm^{-1} can be assigned to aliphatic and aromatic C-H. The aromatic C=C stretching frequency appeared at 1441 cm^{-1} . The C=O stretching frequency appeared at 1728 cm^{-1} . The FTIR spectra of the protective film formed on the metal surface after immersion in HCl and NaOH solutions are shown in Figure 4 and 5 respectively. It is found that almost all the peaks observed for Henna extract are also identified for Sn-sheet immersed in 1 M HCl and 1 M NaOH solution containing 50 mg/L of Henna extract. The phenolic -OH stretching has shifted from 3272 cm^{-1} to 3305 and 3650 cm^{-1} in the acidic medium and 3281 cm^{-1} , 3558 cm^{-1} in the basic medium. The aromatic C=C stretching shifted from 1441 cm^{-1} to 1460 cm^{-1} and 1458 cm^{-1} in the HCl and NaOH solution respectively. The C=O stretching frequency has been shifted from 1728 cm^{-1} to 1743 cm^{-1} in both HCl and NaOH solutions. This indicates formation of Tin-Plant extract complexes or salts. The phenol group of lawsone would donate electron to the metal in order to achieve its noble state of orbit, while the metal would receive the electron to become more stable, hence the metal surface could be protected from the corrosion attack by hindering the redox process [16].

5. Conclusion

The corrosion inhibition behaviour of *Lawsonia inermis* leaves extract on tin metal in 1M HCl and 1 M NaOH for 3 hrs and 4 hrs respectively were investigated using weight loss method. The obtained results showed that, as the corrosion rate was found to increase with increasing in temperature over time, the optimum temperature were determined at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 1 M acid and alkaline solutions comparatively. The inhibition was found to be maximum at an optimum concentration and low temperature due to the inhibitive action of *Lawsonia inermis* leaves extract. *Lawsonia inermis* leaves extract has proved to be an excellent inhibitor for tin in NaOH alkaline solution due to the presence of lawsone. The adsorption takes place via physical adsorption mechanism and Freundlich adsorption model best described the inhibition process. The presence of the compound adsorbed on the tin coupons was verified by spectroscopic measurements of the surface before and after corrosion tests.

Conflict of Interest

The author declared no conflict of interest.

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References

- [1] Rajendran S, Agasta M, Devi B.R, Devi S. B, Rajam k and Jeyasundari (2009). Corrosion inhibition by an aqueous extract of Henna leaves (*Lawsonia Inermis* L). *Scientific paper UDC*, 20: 77-83.
- [2] Al-Sehaibani H (2000). Evaluation of extraction of Henna leaves as environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitor for metals. *Materialwisson Schafund work Stofftochnlk*, 12: 1060-1063.
- [3] Muhammad A.A, Uzairu A, Iyun J.F and Abba H (2014). The use of glutamic acid as corrosion inhibitor for aluminium in HCl solution. *IOSR Journal of Applied Chermistry*, 7: 45-49.
- [4] Ibrahim M. B (2007). Selected experiments in physical chemistry. *Bayero University Kano*, 1-6.

- [5] Nnanna L.A, Anozie I.U, Avoaja A.G.I, Akoma C.S. and Eti E.P (2011). Comparative study of corrosion inhibition of aluminium alloy of type AA3003 in acidic and alkaline media by euphorbia Hirta Extract. *African Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 8: 265- 271.
- [6] Kumpawat N, Chaturvedi A, Upadhyay R.K (2012). Comparative study of corrosion inhibition efficiency of naturally occurring ecofriendly varieties of holy basil for Tin in HNO₃ solution. *Open Journal of Metal*, 2: 68-73.
- [7] Sharma K.S (2012). Basics of corrosion chemistry. *Published by Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH and Co. KGaA*, 1: 1-6.
- [8] James A.O and Akaranta O (2009). The inhibition of corrosion of zinc in 2.0 M hydrochloric acid solution with acetone extract of red onion skin. *African Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 11: 212-218.
- [9] Ituen E.B, Udo U.E, Odozi N.W and Dan E. U (2013). Adsorption and kinetic/ thermodynamic characterization of aluminium corrosion inhibition in sulphuric acid by extract of *Astonia boonei*. *IOSR Journal of Applied Chemistry*, 3:52-59.
- [10] Nwabanne J.T and Okafor V. N (2011). Inhibition of the corrosion of mild steel in acidic medium by vernonia amygdalina: adsorption and thermodynamics study. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 4: 619-625.
- [11] Hamdy A and Nour Sh. El-Gendy (2012). Thermodynamic, adsorption and electrochemical studies for corrosion inhibition of carbon steel by Henna extract in acid medium. *Egyptian Journal of Petroleum*, 1: 17-24.
- [12] Rani A.B.E and Basu J.B.B (2012). Green inhibitors for corrosion protection of metals and alloys: an overview. *International Journal of Corrosion*, 1: 1-15.
- [13] Kaewprasit C, Hequet E, Abidi N and Gouriot J. P (1998). Application of methylene blue adsorption to cotton fiber specific surface area measurement: Part 1. Methodology. *Journal of Cotton Science*, 2: 164-173.
- [14] Cruz J, Martínez-Palou R, Genesca J, García-Ochoa E, (2004). Experimental and theoretical study of 1-(2-ethylamino)-2-methylimidazole as an inhibitor of carbon steel corrosion in acid media. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry*, 1: 111-121.
- [15] Robert G. A and Francis A. C (1990). Organic chemistry: a brief course second edition. *WCB/ McGraw-Hill, USA New York Mexico City*, 491-517.
- [16] Hasan K.S and Sisodia P (2011). Paniaala (*Flacourtia Jangomes*) plant extract as ecofriendly inhibitor on the corrosion of mild steel in acidic media. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, 3: 548-55.